

Isolation of a New Anthraquinone Pigment

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Cassia grandis (Leguminosae) occurs in Northern region of the country. Pulp from the pods of this plant is reported to be a powerful laxative. Seeds polysaccharide of this plant consists of main chain of (1→4)linked galactose and mannose repeating units to which are attached side-chain of (1→3)linked galactose and mannose moieties¹. A flavone glycoside² and two anthraquinone glycosides³ have been isolated from the seeds of plant. Earlier we reported a few anthraquinones⁴ from its roots. Here we report the isolation of a new anthraquinone pigment, grandisone (1,3,4,5,8-pentahydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methylanthraquinone) from the ethyl acetate extract of the roots of this plant.

The ethyl acetate extract of air-dried crushed pieces of roots of *C. grandis* on column chromatography yielded a pigment, C₁₆H₁₂O₈, which gave colour reactions⁵ and uv absorption^{6,7} characteristic of hydroxyanthraquinone. Isolation of 2-methylanthracene by Zn-dust distillation of the pigment showed it to be a 2-methylanthraquinone derivative. The pigment was analysed for one C-methyl, five hydroxyls (penta-acetate) and one methoxyl groups⁷. The ir spectral data suggested the presence of one β-hydroxyl (3 450 cm⁻¹), one methyl (2 892 cm⁻¹), one methoxyl (2 910 and 1 185 cm⁻¹)⁹ and four α-hydroxyl (1 590 cm⁻¹)¹⁰ groups. Solubility of the pigment in 5% aq. Na₂CO₃ solution¹¹ and uv absorption at 377 nm⁷ supported the presence of β-hydroxyl group. The pigment gave characteristic colour reactions of 1,3,4,5,8-pentahydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone^{11,12}. Thus, the OCH₃ group was attached either at C-6 or C-7.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the pigment showed signals corresponding to one C-methyl (δ 2.28, 3H, s, C-2), one methoxyl (3.94, 3H, s, C-6 or 7), one aromatic proton (7.16, 1H, s, H-6 or 7) and five hydroxyl (12.04, 1H, s, C-3; 12.94, 4H, s, C-1, C-4, C-5, C-8) groups. The pigment on KMnO₄ oxidation gave 3,6-dihydroxy-4-methoxyphthalic acid which can result from both the proposed structures. A distinction between the two structures can be drawn only from the ir spectral data of its demethylated derivative. As for the 1,6-dihydroxy compounds, the aromatic absorption is split into two bands around 1 600 and 1 580 cm⁻¹, whereas 1,7-dihydroxy compounds show one very strong absorption band at 1 580 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 13). The ir spectrum of the demethylated derivative of the pigment exhibited one very

strong band at 1 582 cm⁻¹, thus supporting 1,7-dihydroxy system. The foregoing facts establish the structure of the anthraquinone pigment as 1,3,4,5,8-pentahydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methylanthraquinone.

Experimental

The air-dried crushed pieces of roots of *C. grandis* exhaustively extracted in a soxhlet extractor using petroleum ether, benzene and ethyl acetate in succession. A brown coloured compound was isolated from ethyl acetate extract by column chromatography over silica gel column using benzene : ethyl acetate (4 : 6, v/v) as eluant. The pigment was crystallised as brown needles from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-ethyl acetate mixture (1 : 2, v/v), C₁₆H₁₂O₈, m.p. 265–67° (Found : C, 57.53; H, 3.42. C₁₆H₁₂O₈ requires : C, 57.83; H, 3.61%; Found : methoxy, 9.25. Requires : 9.33%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 295, 377, 475, 504, 542, 558 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 200, 2 910, 2 892, 1 640, 1 590, 1 260, 1 185, 970, 730–720 cm⁻¹; acetyl derivative, C₂₆H₂₂O₁₃, m.p. 228° (Found : acetyl, 54.18. Requires : 54.42%); O-methyl derivative, C₂₁H₂₂O₈, m.p. 213° (Found : methoxy, 46.12. Requires : 46.26%); demethylated derivative (boiled with excess of HI (d. 1.7) for 12 h), C₁₅H₁₀O₈, m.p. 290–93°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 220, 2 890, 1 640, 1 582, 1 250, 1 160 and 730 cm⁻¹.

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NOTE

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